

ISic3089

I.Sicily inscription 3089

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Cephaloedium

Place of origin (modern)

Cefalù

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Cefalù, Duomo (?)

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331405

1. ὁ δᾶμο [ς τῶν Κεφαλοιδιτᾶν]
2. Λεύκιον Δο [— — — — — — —]
3. Γναίου □ υἱωνὸ [ν — — — —]
4. εὐνοίας ἔνεκα.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284882

EDCS 64900517

PHI 331405

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum*

graecum. At 36.0845

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1982. II materiale antico reimpiegato e rilavorato in età normanna - Iscrizioni greche. *Mostra di documenti e testimonianze figurative della Basilica Ruggeriana di Cefalù. Catalogo della mostra Cefalù, luglio - settembre 1982*. Palermo. pp. 63-64. At 63-64 ph

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-23): ISic3089. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4388103>